

➔ **From start to finish:** All sciencewalks start at the Zytglogge clock tower. Each walk includes directions – for those who prefer strolling through the city to scrolling around Google Maps or fiddling with a paper map. Most hotspots are located outside of the Aare peninsula. Bern's university district Länggasse is north of the railway station.

🗨️ **By the way:** Find brief descriptions of noteworthy, interesting, and downright surprising facts under this heading.

↗️ **Just around the corner:** Check here for more sights and activities in the area – for those who like to take the long way, or even the wrong way.

1 Hallerstrasse, Haller Statue Grosse Schanze

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Schanzenstrasse – Hochschulstrasse – Grosse Schanze.

2 University House, Kocherpark

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Hirschengraben – Effingerstrasse – Belpstrasse.

3 House of Academies

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Laupenstrasse.

4 Tumarkinweg

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Schanzenstrasse – Hochschulstrasse – Tumarkinweg.

5 Studerstein, «Bei den Eichen» (By the Oaks)

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Schanzenstrasse – Länggassstrasse – Mittelstrasse – Neubrücke – Studerstrasse.

6 University of Bern's main building, Grosse Schanze

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Schanzenstrasse – Hochschulstrasse – Grosse Schanze.

7 Gertrud-Woker-Strasse

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Schanzenstrasse – Länggassstrasse – Bühlstrasse – Bühlplatz – Gertrud-Woker-Strasse.

8 Einstein Museum

➔ Zytglogge – Kramgasse – Münstergässli – Münsterplatz – Münsterplattform.

9 UniS

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Schanzenstrasse – Schanzeneckstrasse.

10 Anna-Seiler-Fountain

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Anna-Seiler-Fountain – Käfigturm.

11 Huberstrasse

➔ Zytglogge – Theaterplatz – Casinoplatz – Kochergasse – Bundesgasse – Effingerstrasse – Loryplatz – Schlossstrasse – Huberstrasse.

12 Botanical Garden

➔ Zytglogge – Kornhausplatz – Zeughausgasse – Aarberggasse – Genfergasse – Hodlerstrasse – Paul-Klee-Square – Lorrainebrücke – Botanical Gardens.

13 Zentrum Paul Klee

➔ Zytglogge – Kramgasse – Gerechtigkeitsgasse – Nydeggasse – Nydeggbücke – Grosser Muristalden – Schlosshaldenstrasse – Zentrum Paul Klee.

14 "Chemical Landmark", Holzkofenweg 36

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Hirschengraben – Effingerstrasse – Monbijoustrasse – Wander – Holzkofenweg.

15 Unitobler

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Schanzenstrasse – Falkenplatz – Länggassstrasse.

16 Climate and Prof Thomas Stocker

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Schanzenstrasse – Hochschulstrasse.

17 Federal Palace

➔ Zytglogge – Theaterplatz – Casinoplatz – Kochergasse – Bundesgasse – Bundesterrasse.

18 Insel area, sitem-insel

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Laupenstrasse – Murtenstrasse – Freiburgstrasse.

19 Sustainability and Prof Peter Messerli

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Schanzenstrasse – Länggassstrasse – Mittelstrasse.

20 Building for Exact Sciences

➔ Zytglogge – Marktgasse – Spitalgasse – Railway Station – Bubenbergplatz – Schanzenstrasse – Sidlerstrasse.

21 Casino Bern

➔ Zytglogge – Theaterplatz – Casinoplatz.

